

Inflation of the number of infections prevented by COVID-19 vaccination in Kayano et al.'s paper

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In October 2023, a paper on counterfactual simulations of COVID-19 cases and deaths using transmission models was published [1]. This paper, titled “Evaluating the COVID-19 vaccination program in Japan, 2021 using the counterfactual reproduction number,” claims that “the total effectiveness of the vaccination program in preventing infection and death was estimated at 92.6% and 97.2%, respectively.”

Although the corresponding author of the paper, Hiroshi Nishiura, had not responded to our repeated requests to provide us with the source code of their simulator for a long time, he finally published the source code of the program used for the computation in the paper [2]. Although it is recorded that the technical metadata was created on April 19, 2025, the publication date is claimed to be October 18, 2023.

Since the surveillance data of COVID-19 infections were not provided in [2], the data provided in [3], which were generated by reading the graph in [1], were used in the following analysis. By feeding this data in addition to the other provided datasets, the program provided in [2] was successfully run, as shown in Figure 1. When the reporting coverage of infection is assumed to be 25%, the estimated cumulative number of infections almost quadruples, as shown in Figure 2, which is consistent with the results in [1].

Figure 1. Reproduced results based on the source code provided in [2] (100% reporting coverage).

Figure 2. Reproduced results based on the source code provided in [2] (25% reporting coverage).

The paper [1] claims that the number of infections $i_{a,t}$ in age group a at time t in the counterfactual simulation is given by

$$i_{a,t} = \sum_{b=1}^{10} \sum_{\tau=1}^{t-1} R_{ab,t} i_{b,t-\tau} g_{\tau},$$

where g_{τ} indicates the probability density function of the generation interval, while the effective reproduction number $R_{ab,t}$, which is interpreted as the average number of secondary cases in age group a generated by a single primary case in age group b at calendar time t , is given by

$$R_{ab,t} = (1 - l_{a,t} - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{t-1} i_{a,k}}{n_a}) K_{ab} p h_t d_t c_t.$$

Here $l_{a,t}$ denotes the immune fraction in age group a at calendar time t , which is based on the estimated efficacy of vaccines, while $\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{t-1} i_{a,k}}{n_a}$ represents the cumulative number of previous infections.

In the source code of the counterfactual simulation provided in [2], however, the definition of $i_{a,t}$ is different between the vaccination scenario and the non-vaccination scenario. The corresponding part of the source code reads:

```

for(a in 1:m){
  if(vac_program == 1){
    jb = colSums(previous_expect[(t2-14):(t2-1),b+1]*diag_bias*generation(14)[14:1])
    gt_ja_pre[t2,a] = sum(as.matrix(NGM)[a,] * (1 - (imm_frac_df[t,a+1] + sum(previous_expect[1:(t2-1),a+1]*diag_bias)/N[a])) * all_para * jb)
  } else {
    jb = colSums(gt_ja_pre[(t2-14):(t2-1),b]*generation(14)[14:1])
    gt_ja_pre[t2,a] = sum(as.matrix(NGM)[a,] * (1 - sum(gt_ja_pre[1:(t2-1),a])/N[a]) * all_para * jb)
  }
}

```

In this program, the parameter “previous_expect” is given by the real-world surveillance data. Therefore, the simulated number of infections in the vaccination scenario (vac_program == 1) is calculated from the recent number of infections in the surveillance data, meaning that the future is predicted based on the real-world data of the recent past. In this case, the simulated results fit well with the infection curve in the surveillance data.

In the non-vaccination scenario, however, the number of infections is calculated recursively, as is usually done in the numerical solution of differential equations. To fairly compare the two scenarios, the same calculations should be applied for both scenarios, as shown below:

```

for(a in 1:m){
  if(vac_program == 1){
    jb = colSums(gt_ja_pre[(t2-14):(t2-1),b]*generation(14)[14:1])
    gt_ja_pre[t2,a] = sum(as.matrix(NGM)[a,] * (1 - (imm_frac_df[t,a+1] + sum(gt_ja_pre[1:(t2-1),a])/N[a])) * all_para * jb)
  } else {
    jb = colSums(gt_ja_pre[(t2-14):(t2-1),b]*generation(14)[14:1])
    gt_ja_pre[t2,a] = sum(as.matrix(NGM)[a,] * (1 - sum(gt_ja_pre[1:(t2-1),a])/N[a]) * all_para * jb)
  }
}

```

The results of the recursive calculation using the same parameters in the factual case are shown in Figure 3 (100% reporting coverage) and Figure 4 (25% reporting coverage). As these figures show, the number of infections deviates significantly from the actual

surveillance data, which casts doubt on the credibility of the model. Based on this result, it can be argued, paradoxically, that implementing the exact same vaccination program as was done in reality would result in millions more infections than in reality.

Figure 3. Number of infections as the solution to the differential equation under real-world parameters, where the factual vaccination program was administered (100% reporting coverage).

Figure 4. Number of infections as the solution to the differential equation under real-world parameters, where the factual vaccination program was administered (25% reporting coverage).

Below, let us assume that the reporting coverage is 25%, which is mainly used in [1]. Here, the following three numbers of infections are at stake:

- (1) 4.7 million: Number of infections as the solution when fitted to real-world values.
- (2) 12.5 million: Number of infections as the solution to the differential equation under real-world parameters, where the factual vaccination program was administered.

(3) 63.3 million: Number of infections as the solution to the differential equation under counterfactual parameters in which no vaccination program was administered.

Note that the values in (1) and (3) are taken from [1], while the value in (2) is taken from Figure 4 of this paper. Kayano et al. claim that the number of infections is drastically decreased by comparing the numbers (1) and (3). However, a fair comparison should be made between (2) and (3), while mentioning the large discrepancy between (1) and (2), which suggests that their model may overestimate infections by nearly threefold. Based on a simple proportional estimation, the numbers of infections and deaths prevented by the vaccination programs, 58.6 million and 354,000 respectively according to [1], fall to about one third of their reported values. This issue, however, was not addressed in their paper. This is a misleading argument designed to inflate the efficacy of the COVID-19 vaccine, which is highly likely to constitute questionable research practice.

On September 1, 2025, the Japanese Association for Infectious Diseases, the Japanese Respiratory Society, and the Japanese Society for Vaccinology jointly issued a statement endorsing the 2025 regular COVID-19 vaccination program [4], citing the simulation results of Kayano et al. as justification. It is noteworthy and unfortunate that none of the members of these three societies, which amount to more than 20,000, identified the flaw in Kayano et al.'s simulations for more than four months after the source code was published.

Given the social impact of the paper, a thorough and rigorous review of the methodology and an investigation into possible scientific misconduct are warranted.

Conflict of Interests

The author declares no competing interests exist.

Finding

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References

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[3] <https://github.com/yoshiumeno/transmit>

[4] https://www.kansensho.or.jp/uploads/files/news/gakkai/gakkai_covid19_250902.pdf